

Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons. Part IX. Cationoid Alkylation of Acenaphthene with Ethyl Allylacetate

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Cationoid alkylation of acenaphthene with ethyl allylacetate has been studied and 10-methyl-, and 7,10-dimethylacenaphthenes have been synthesized.

The Colonge-Mukherji¹ cyclialkylation/cyclodehydration method has been used for the synthesis of homologues of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons which have potential tumorigenic properties as compared to the parent hydrocarbon². This method has been studied rather extensively by Mukherji *et al.* in the field of naphthalene³, phenanthrene⁴, 3,4-benzphenanthrene⁵, tetraphene⁶, benzotetraphene⁷ and anthraceno-(1',2':1,2)-anthracene⁷ and appears promising for the facile production of certain hitherto unknown polynuclear hydrocarbons. In this paper we record the results obtained during the synthesis of methyl substituted acenaphthenes through cationoid alkylation of acenaphthene with ethyl allylacetate.

Acenaphthene, on condensation with ethyl allylacetate in presence of aluminium chloride, gave γ -(5-acenaphthyl) valerate (I) in 40% yield. The orientation of the product was established by hydrolysing the ester (I) with 20% alcoholic potassium hydroxide followed by cyclisation to ketone (II) with polyphosphoric acid, in 75% yield. This ketone was found to be identical with the one obtained from the known β -(5-acenaphthoyl) propionic acid as shown.

β -(5-Acenaphthoyl) propionic acid (IV), prepared by the method of Fieser and Peters⁸, was esterified with ethyl alcohol and sulphuric acid. The ester (V) on reaction with methyl magnesium iodide gave γ -(5'-acenaphthyl)- $\Delta^{3:4}$ -pentenonic acid which was

1. Barclay, "Cyclialkylation of Aromatics" in G.A. Olah's "Friedel-Crafts and Related Reactions", Interscience, 1960, Vol. I, Part II, page 785-977.
2. Badger, Nat. Cancer Inst. Monograph, (1962) No. 9, p. 1.
3. Mukherji *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1499; Mukherji *et al.*, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 1.
4. Mukherji and Bhattacharyya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1202.
5. Mukherji *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 328; Gaiind *et al.*, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 53, 1.
6. Vig *et al.*, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 697; Mukherji *et al.*, *ibid.* 1965, 177; Gandhi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1957, 163
7. K. S. Sharma, Ph D. Thesis, 1965 (The University, Kurukshetra).
8. Fieser and Peters, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4373.

reduced to (VII) with phosphorus and hydroiodic acid in 70% yield. The acid (VII) was cyclized with polyphosphoric acid to give a ketone identical with the one described earlier.

γ -(5-Acenaphthyl) valeric acid cyclized at position-4 to give 7-keto-10-methyl-7,8,9,10-tetrahydroacenaphthrene (III). The orientation is based on the analogy with the cyclization of γ -(5-acenaphthyl) butyric acid⁹ at 4-position favouring a 6-membered ring formation, contrary to the behaviour shown by β -(5-acenaphthoyl) propionic acid which cyclizes at 6-position producing a 7-membered ring (here substitution ortho to unsaturated group impedes the reaction⁹). Literature does not record any instance where a methyl group substituted at γ -position has altered the direction of cyclization of substituted butyric acid. Evidently γ -(5-acenaphthyl) valeric acid should behave in a manner similar to γ -(5-acenaphthyl)butyric acid.

The ketone (III) was reduced by Clemmensen's method to 10-methyl-7,8,9,10-tetrahydroacenaphthrene (VIII) in 85% yield. This compound was dehydrogenated with 30% palladium charcoal at 300-320° to 10-methylacenaphthrene (IX) in 60% yield, whereas Fieser and Peters have obtained acenaphthrene in only 26% yield. The hydrocarbon (IX) was characterized by its picrate m.p. 150°.

The ketone (III) on Grignard's reaction with methyl magnesium iodide gave 7,10-dimethyl-9,10-dihydroacenaphthrene (X) which after aromatization gave 7,10-dimethylacenaphthrene (XI) (picrate m.p. 175°).

EXPERIMENTAL

Boiling points and melting points are uncorrected.

Ethyl-γ-(5-acenaphthyl) valerate (I).—The aluminium chloride-catalyzed reaction between ethyl allylacetate (25.6 g.) and acenaphthene (30.8 g.) in carbon disulphide (60 ml.) in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (54 g.) was carried out under the conditions described by Mukherji and Bhattacharyya⁴. After usual working up and removal of the solvent the residue was distilled to yield wine red viscous oil (22 g.), b.p. 220-25°/5 mm. Yield 40%. (Found: C, 81.26; H, 7.98%; $C_{19}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.85; H, 7.80%).

γ-(5-Acenaphthyl) valeric Acid (II).—Hydrolysis of the above ester (I; 20 g.) with 20% alcoholic potassium hydroxide was effected by refluxing for 12 hr; this gave 16 g. (88%) of the *γ*-(5-acenaphthyl) valeric acid (II), b.p. 235-40°/5mm. (Found: C, 80.83; H, 7.58%; $C_{17}H_{18}O_2$ requires: C, 80.31; H, 7.08%).

7-Keto-10-methyl-7,8,9,10-tetrahydroacephenanthrene (III).—The above acid (II; 16 g.) was subjected to cyclization with polyphosphoric acid and 12 g. of the ketone (III) was obtained, b.p. 235°/3mm. The ketone solidified on cooling and it was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether mixture to give 11g. (75%) light yellow crystals, m.p. 116-17°. (Found: C, 86.1; H, 7.07%; $C_{17}H_{16}O$ requires: C, 86.41; H, 6.77%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared in the usual manner and recrystallized from ethyl acetate which afforded deep red crystals melting at 275°. (Found: N, 13.42%; $C_{23}H_{20}N_4O_4$ requires: N, 13.43%).

β-(5-Acenaphthoyl) propionic Acid (IV).—Acenaphthene (12.5 g.) was subjected to Friedel-Crafts reaction with succinic anhydride (9 g.) in nitrobenzene (50 ml.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (24 g.), following exactly the procedure described by Fieser and Peters⁸. After working up the reaction mixture, in the usual manner, *β*-(5-acenaphthoyl) propionic acid (14 g.) was separated in the prescribed way from its 3-isomer. On crystallization from alcohol white solid (12 g.) melting at 208° was obtained, yield 70% for the 5-isomer.

Ethyl-β-(5-acenaphthoyl) propionate (V).—The above acid (IV; 12 g.), absolute alcohol (70 ml.) and conc. H_2SO_4 (4 ml) were refluxed for 10 hr. After the usual working up, ethyl *β*-(5-acenaphthoyl) propionate (8 g.) was obtained. It was crystallized from methyl alcohol and had m.p. 72-73°, yield 80%. (Found: C, 78.01; H, 6.82%; $C_{18}H_{18}O_2$ requires: C, 78.59; H, 6.38%).

γ-(5'-Acenaphthyl)-Δ^{3:4}-pentenoic Acid (VI).—The ester (V) was subjected to Grignard's reaction with methyl magnesium iodide according to the method of Haworth *et al.*¹⁰. Ester (8 g.) in benzene (50 ml.) was treated with a solution of methyl magnesium iodide prepared from magnesium (0.5 g.) and methyl iodide (2.3 g.) in anhydrous ether (20 ml.). After refluxing for 2 hr. the product was decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was extracted several times with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution. Acidification liberated the acid (3.6 g.) which distilled at 230°/3 mm, yield 67%. (Found: C, 81.18; H, 6.64%; $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ requires: C, 80.95; H, 6.34%).

10. Haworth *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1790.

γ-(5-Acenaphthyl) valeric Acid (VII).—The unsaturated acid (VI; 3.5 g.) was reduced with phosphorus (3.5 g.) and hydroiodic acid (17 ml.) by refluxing for 6 hr. It was worked up as described by Ha₂worth *et al.* After removal of the solvent the residue distilled at 210–15°/3mm. and there was obtained 2.5 g. of the acid (VII) in 70% yield. (Found: C, 80.71; H, 6.83%; C₁₇H₁₈O₂ requires: C, 80.3; H, 7.08%).

7-Keto-10-methyl-7,8,9,10-tetrahydroacephenanthrene (III).—The above acid (VII; 2 g.) was cyclized with polyphosphoric acid and the ketone (III) was obtained in 75% yield which after two crystallizations from petroleum ether melted at 116° and remained undepressed when mixed with the earlier sample. (Found: C, 86.01; H, 7.02%; C₁₇H₁₆O requires: C, 86.41; H, 6.77%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 275° and remained undepressed when mixed with the earlier sample. (Found: N, 13.05%; C₂₃H₂₀N₄O₄ requires: N, 13.43%).

10-Methyl-7,8,9,10-tetrahydroacephenanthrene (VIII).—The ketone (III; 6 g.) was reduced according to modified Clemmensen's method, using amalgamated zinc (12 g.), conc. HCl (18 ml.), water (9 ml.), toluene (15 ml.) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 25 hr. Conc. HCl (6 ml.) was added after every 6 hr. After removal of the solvent the residue distilled at 210–20°/3 mm. and 4.7 g. (85%) of the reduced product (VIII) was obtained. (Found: C, 91.48; H, 7.98%; C₁₇H₁₈ requires: C, 91.89; H, 8.10%).

10-Methylacephenanthrene (IX).—The above compound (VIII; 2 g.) was heated with 30% palladium charcoal (0.25 g.) at 300–320° in the atmosphere of carbon dioxide for 6 hr. The hydrocarbon thus obtained was crystallised from benzene-alcohol to give light yellow crystals (1.1 g.; 60%), m.p. 195°.

The analytical sample was prepared by regenerating the hydrocarbon from its picrate by passing the solution of the picrate in benzene through a column of alumina. (Found: C, 93.87; H, 6.12%; C₁₇H₁₄ requires: C, 93.57; H, 6.45%).

U. V. Spectra:	226 (4.39); 251 (4.99); 291 (4.07);
λ _{max} (cyclohexane)	320 (4.03); 368 (2.75) and 388 (2.45) mμ (log ε).
I.R. spectra:	ν _{max} 2900, 1600, 1450, 1380, 1290, 1150, 1080, 1040,
	Nujol 975, 905, 875, 778, 765, 725 cm ⁻¹ .

The picrate, prepared in benzene, was crystallized from ethanol which gave dark brown needles melting at 150°. No increase in the m.p. was observed on repeated crystallizations. (Found: N, 9.44%; C₂₃H₁₈N₃O₇ requires: N, 9.18%).

7,10-Dimethyl-9,10-dihydroacephenanthrene (X).—The ketone (III; 5g.) was treated with a solution of methyl magnesium iodide prepared from magnesium (0.8 g.) and methyl iodide (6 g.) in dry ether (50 ml). The solution was refluxed for 2 hr. After the usual working up the residue was heated with a crystal of iodine and distilled under reduced pressure to give highly viscous liquid (4 g.; 82%), b.p. 210–20°/3 mm. It was crystallized from petroleum ether to give colourless crystal, m.p. 155°. (Found: C, 92.01; H, 7.79%; C₁₉H₁₈ requires: C, 92.30; H, 7.69%).

7-10-Dimethylacephenanthrene (XI).—The hydroaromatic compound (X; 2g.) was smoothly dehydrogenated with 0.2 g. of 30% palladium charcoal at 300-320° in the atmosphere of carbon dioxide, by heating for 6 hr. After usual working up and crystallization from benzene-alcohol mixture was thus obtained 1.2 g. (60%) of a light yellow coloured solid which melted at 135°. It was regenerated from its picrate for the analytical sample. (Found: C, 92.56; H, 7.32%; $C_{18}H_{16}$ requires: C, 93.10; H, 6.89%).

The reddish brown picrate was prepared in benzene solution and was crystallized from absolute ethyl alcohol which melted at 175°. (Found: N, 9.60%; $C_{14}H_{10}N_3O_7$ requires: N, 9.11%).

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